

EFFECTIVE USE OF PROMISING AREAS OF SMALL ENTERPRISES

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Annotation: The article covers important points about effective use of promising areas of small enterprises. On the other hand, types of advertising which are used to increase the brand awareness for the end user were noted.

Key words: *post-industrial economies, social 'environmental conditions', crowd-out investment, neighbourhood-level services, end customers, dealer network.*

Innovation development today is recognized as the most promising way to create a highly efficient modern economy in the vast majority of countries in the world. Many countries have already made positive progress by moving towards the creation of post-industrial economies. In addition to the direct economic effects of making new services and products available and creating employment, the SME has several equally important effects on the functioning of transitional societies that move through more indirect channels. The development of this sector is essential to create the political and social 'environmental conditions' necessary to allow desirable changes to occur elsewhere in the system. The SME sector must simultaneously absorb resources and workers from the large enterprise sector and at the same time help to create a labour market situation in which the process of reorientation and fundamental reorganization of the large enterprise sector can be carried through without threatening social peace. In addition to slowing down the restructuring process, the failure to develop the

SME may increase the volume of required transfer payments for unemployment, early retirement and other programmes and (under certain fiscal policy assumptions) crowd-out investment and other employment creating expenditures. The complexity of creating and sustaining the development of a SME sector in an emerging transitional economy becomes evident as soon as attention shifts beyond the more obvious retail and neighbourhood-level services and considers directly productive small enterprises. Preliminary comparisons among China, Russia, other FSU countries, Hungary, Poland, Czech Republic and Slovak Republic support this view[1]. Existing institutions and ‘capabilities’, including the extent of formation and survival of networks and other embedded relationships, appear to interact with the active policy measures and the legal environment to determine the transition period performance of the sector.

In order to increase sales, the company strives to achieve the highest quality of its own products and services. Therefore, this area is paid a lot of attention. To this end, construction companies create quality services that monitor compliance with the technological process, check the quality of raw materials coming to the enterprise. If we talk about the consumers of products of surveyed the small construction companies under study, they can be divided into three main categories:

- end customers - individuals who buy products for personal needs;
- construction companies, designers, architects who purchase products for the execution of works for the order;
- dealers specializing in distributing products.

Most of the clients in the first category are people with high and middle level of income. They are the owners of apartments, country cottages, houses for permanent residence. The second group consists of companies that carry out the construction of housing and office space. In this case, the products of small construction enterprises are used for the construction and design of cottage

settlements and country houses, as well as for creating original design solutions for prestigious urban housing. The final purchasing group is represented by numerous dealers distributing products through their own sales systems. Sales of products and services of most of the small construction companies under surveillance take place through their own sales department and dealer network[2]. The population accounts for about 32% of total sales. This is the most interesting and promising sales channel, as the sale of products is carried out at maximum prices without delays and often without discounts. If we consider the long-term prospects for the development of small construction companies, the increase in sales volumes may continue mainly due to the development of new markets. And the potential of the local market is not exhausted to the end. This is evident due to the growth of the suburban real estate market and the construction materials market. Small construction companies pay great attention to maintaining the image of the brand and sales promotion. For these purposes, there are advertising departments at enterprises that promote products on the market. To increase the brand awareness for the end user, the following types of advertising are used:

- Mailing of letters.
- Outdoor advertising (banners along roads).
- Catalogs, flyers, booklets.
- Articles in weekly advertising and information publications related to suburban real estate and construction.
- Complex measures for the creation of the brand (diplomas, awards, certificates).
- Participation in industrial and specialized construction exhibitions.
- SMM (social media marketing).
- Digital marketing[3].

In banking and financial services, the energy and resource extraction sectors,

and some manufacturing product areas such as passenger vehicles, the trend toward ever-larger scale has continued, but in the rest of the economy a different story seemed to be emerging. Of course even the most ardent advocates of large-scale production did not expect all products and services to follow this path. But Piore and Sabel were suggesting that even within the sphere of industrial production small might be the wave of the future, at least for non-commodity products. Piore and Sabel concluded that the SME sector may be developing a competitive advantage based on flexibility and speed of adaptation in areas where the possibilities of realizing further scale economies are weak or non-existent. Certain types of transactions, especially services, seem to have an automatic and self-limiting aspect, requiring face-to-face individual exchange. Some of the seemingly safe retail and service preserves of the SME have in fact already been taken over by large firms. The establishment of bakeries, photo-finishing and auto parts departments and full service drug stores within large American-style food stores are examples. The European hypermarket carries these trends to their logical conclusion. Another example is the formation of large chains that employ highly trained professional workers on an hourly wage basis to provide optical, medical, dental or legal services. In some of these product areas a national or international brand identity has been established for products and services that once seemed to define personalized exchanges and SME scale.

In a summary it should be noted that the Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) sector carries great hopes and great burdens in the evolution of all of the transitional economies. Sustained and healthy growth of this sector is obviously necessary, since it is difficult to imagine rising overall living standards and social peace without such a development. With the large-scale units of both the State-Owned Enterprise (SOE) and previously State-Owned Enterprise (PSOE) sector often at best stagnant, successful performance during the transition increasingly appears to be dependent on the expansion of this Small and Medium Enterprise

sector. Even if the hopes that this sector will by itself have a systems-dynamizing and transformational effect prove to be false, its role in generating employment and an atmosphere of social stability is crucial.

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